

NOTES

Alcoholic extract: The remaining alcoholic extractive, on chromatography over silica gel column yielded following compounds.

Astragalin: Obtained as yellow crystalline product m.p. 180° (Lit. 178°)⁴. It responded to shinoda (Mg+HCl) and Molisch's tests. On acid hydrolysis it yielded an aglycone (methanol) m.p. 275-77° (Lit. 275-76°)⁵. The aglycone was identified as kaempferol by paper chromatography and spectral data.

Rutin-Acetone: Alcohol (2:8) eluted fractions furnished rutin as yellow microcrystalline substance m.p. 185-86°. On hydrolysis with alc. 7% HCl, it furnished quercetin m.p. 312-15° (Lit. 313-14°)⁴. The latter gave an acetate m.p. 194-95°. The glucose and rhamnose were identified in hydrolysate by p.c.

Quercetin: On elution with alcohol quercetin was obtained as a yellow crystalline product m.p. 309-11°.

Aqueous extract: Glucose and galactose along with mannitol were detected in the aqueous extract by two dimensional p.c. The aqueous extract of the alcohol exhausted leaves gave potassium oxalate (0.001%).

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Synthesis of Some New 4-Arylhydrazone-N'-Arylthiocarbamoyl-3-Methyl-2-Pyrazolin-5-Ones as Possible Potential Antidiabetics

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A series of pyrazolin-5-one derivatives, viz., 4-arylhydrazone-N'-phenylthiocarbamoyl-(I_a), 4-arylhydrazone-N'-3-methylphenylthiocarbamoyl-(I_b), 4-arylhydrazone-N'-4-methylphenylthiocarbamoyl-(I_c), 4-arylhydrazone-N'-3-methoxyphenylthiocarbamoyl-(I_d) and 4-arylhydrazone-N'-4-methoxyphenylthiocarbamoyl-(I_e) have been synthesised as possible potential oral antidiabetics.

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| (I _a) R' = C ₆ H ₅ | (I _d) R' = <i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ |
| (I _b) R' = <i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ | (I _e) R' = <i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ |
| (I _c) R' = <i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ | |

The compounds described in this communication have been synthesised by reacting ethyl-2, 3-dioxobutyrate-2-arylhydrazones with different derivatives of phenylthiosemicarbazides. The structures of these compounds have been established on the basis of ir and mass spectral studies. The reactivity of ethyl-2, 3-dioxobutyrate-2-arylhydrazones was smooth and the products were obtained in good yield. The reactivity followed the expected course, diazonium chloride with electron withdrawing group in position 2 and 4 gave better yields. Colour of all these compounds ranges from yellow to orange.

Experimental

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra were taken in KBr film on a Beckmann IR spectrophotometer. Mass spectral studies were carried out on a Varian Mat-CH-7 mass spectrophotometer. Ethyl-2, 3-dioxobutyrate-2-arylhydrazones were prepared by the reported method¹.

Preparation of 4-arylhydrazone-N'-phenylthiocarbamoyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one:

Ethyl-2,3-dioxobutyrate-2-arylhydrazone (0.002 mol) was dissolved in alcohol (25 ml), a hot solution

of phenylthiosemicarbazide (0.002 ml) in alcohol was added and the mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs. On cooling shining crystals separated out which were recrystallised from 80% ethyl alcohol. Anal: m.p. 168°. Calculated for C₁₇H₁₅N₅OS : N, 20.7%.

Found : N, 20.8% $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1540 cm⁻¹ (NH-N=C-), 1710 cm⁻¹ (C=O cyclic); 3440 cm⁻¹ (-NH), 1650 cm⁻¹ (C=C or C=N), and 850-750 cm⁻¹ (substituted phenyl); M⁺ at m/e 337.

4-Arylhydrazono-N'-3-methylphenylthiocarbamoyl- /4-methylphenylthiocarbamoyl- /3-methoxyphenylthiocarbamoyl- /4-methoxyphenylthiocarbamoyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-ones were prepared in the same way by taking suitably substituted phenylthiosemicarbazide. Their characteristics are compiled in Table 1.

TABLE 1--CHARACTERISTICS OF 4-ARYLHYDRAZONO-N'-ARYLTHIOCARBAMOYL-3-METHYL-2-PYRAZOLIN-5-ONES

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	m.p. °C	Yield %
1	2	3	4	5
1.	H	C ₆ H ₅	168	50
2.	2-CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	205	55
3.	3-CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	195	60
4.	4-CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	163	60
5.	2-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	158	55
6.	3-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	165	45
7.	4-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	145	45
8.	2-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	170	40
9.	3-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	150	60
10.	4-Cl	C ₆ H ₅	172	55
11.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	163	60
12.	2-NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	172	65
13.	3-NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	165	60
14.	4-NO ₂	C ₆ H ₅	215	65
15.	H	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	148	45
16.	2-CH ₃	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	180	50
17.	3-CH ₃	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	179	45
18.	4-CH ₃	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	133	45
19.	2-OCH ₃	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	145	50
20.	3-OCH ₃	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	155	50
21.	4-OCH ₃	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	136	55
22.	2-Cl	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	175	55
23.	3-Cl	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	135	45
24.	4-Cl	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	130	45
25.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	140	55
26.	2-NO ₂	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	175	60
27.	4-NO ₂	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	213	60

(Table 1 Contd.)

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	m.p. °C	Yield %
1	2	3	4	5
28.	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	130	50
29.	2-CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	180	55
30.	3-CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	179	60
31.	4-CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	145	55
32.	2-OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	145	50
33.	3-OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	155	50
34.	4-OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	136	50
35.	2-Cl	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	175	60
36.	3-Cl	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	135	55
37.	4-Cl	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	135	60
38.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	140	55
39.	2-NO ₂	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	175	60
40.	4-NO ₂	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	215	65
41.	H	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	115	65
42.	2-CH ₃	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	175	60
43.	3-CH ₃	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	150	60
44.	4-CH ₃	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	120	65
45.	2-OCH ₃	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	167	55
46.	3-OCH ₃	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	150	60
47.	4-OCH ₃	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	138	60
48.	2-Cl	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	132	65
49.	3-Cl	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	142	50
50.	4-Cl	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	125	55
51.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	160	65
52.	2-NO ₂	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	170	65
53.	4-NO ₂	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	210	70
54.	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	192	60
55.	2-CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	190	65
56.	3-CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	185	60
57.	4-CH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	120	55
58.	2-OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	195	55
59.	3-OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	180	60
60.	4-OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	139	55
61.	2-Cl	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	180	65
62.	3-Cl	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	175	65
63.	4-Cl	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	133	50
64.	2-OC ₂ H ₅	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	160	60
65.	2-NO ₂	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	183	65
66.	4-NO ₂	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	215	65

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